

Measurement Results

C1_0411.nzt

Measurement Results

Measurement Type : Zeta Potential
Sample Name : C1
Temperature of the holder : 24.9 °C
Viscosity of the dispersion medium : 0.897 mPa·s
Conductivity : 2.633 mS/cm
Electrode Voltage : 2.8 V

Calculation Results

Peak No.	Zeta Potential	Electrophoretic Mobility
1	-1.2 mV	-0.000009 cm ² /Vs
2	--- mV	--- cm ² /Vs
3	--- mV	--- cm ² /Vs

Zeta Potential (Mean) : -1.2 mV
Electrophoretic Mobility mean : -0.000009 cm²/Vs

